

Distributed Superresolution Gas Source Localization based on Poisson Equation

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Abstract—Accurate modeling and estimation of airborne material in Chemical, Biological, Radiological, or Nuclear accidents are vital for effective disaster response. In this paper a method that combines prior domain knowledge in terms of Partial Differential Equations (PDEs), sparse Bayesian learning (SBL), and cooperative estimation for multiple robots or sensor networks is proposed to identify the number and locations of gas sources. Using method of Green’s functions and the adjoint state method, a gradient-based optimization with respect to source location is derived, allowing superresolving (arbitrary) source locations. By combing the latter with SBL, a sparse source support can be identified, thus indirectly assessing the number of sources. Both steps are computed cooperatively, utilizing the agent network to share information. Simulation results demonstrate the effectiveness of the approach.

I. INTRODUCTION

In case of Chemical, Biological, Radiological, or Nuclear accidents an accurate modeling and estimation of the spatio-temporal evolution of airborne released material is of paramount importance for optimal disaster response. Autonomous mobile robotic platforms, equipped with appropriate sensors, are ideal tools to explore and operate in such environments. Autonomy would imply ability of robots to “learn” their environment to derive optimal operation/control strategies. To this end robots need to rely on prior domain knowledge, such as a gas propagation models, to cope well with data-scarce regime characteristic for perception in non-visual, chemical sensing domain. This is a paradigm we follow in this work.

In general, the physics of a spatio-temporal evolution of dispersed materials can be well described in terms of PDEs. For instance, the non-homogeneous advection-diffusion or scalar transport equation [1] can model propagation of material through the air from several emitting sources. Yet in practice, parameters of these models, such as boundary conditions or the number of sources, are unknown and have to be estimated from data. Collecting such spatially distributed data is also challenging, as these processes are in general dynamic and vary in space. To achieve this, multiple robots can be used to collect spatial samples more efficiently and process them together for real-time responses to new data and process changes. The presented work is therefore dedicated to a cooperative estimation of the parameters of a PDE based on distributed measurements collected by the swarm of interconnected robots or a sensor network. Specifically, we address the Gas Source Localization (GSL) [2] problem of estimating the number and locations of multiple gas sources. We will use a

Poisson equation as a model for steady state gas dispersion, which is a simplification. Yet it can demonstrate the proposed methodology that can be extended to more realistic models.

Traditionally, robot movements in olfaction strategies relied on techniques such as *chemotaxis* [3], [4] and *anemotaxis* [5], [6]. However, these approaches often assume a known number of sources and smooth concentration gradients. Model-based methods offer more promising solutions by building upon the mathematical structure of the process model and treating sources as unknown parameters. This allows for modeling uncertainties [7], using different models [8]–[10], and handling unknown environments [11], [12]. Infotaxis-based methods [13] further enhance model-based GSL by autonomously guiding robots to sources using information-theoretic criteria (see e.g., [13]–[15]). Despite these advancements, most GSL research assumes a fixed and known number of sources due to the computational challenges of integer optimization. However, recent works introduced a combination of SBL [16], [17] and a PDE-based dispersion modeling, relaxing the fixed-source-count assumption [18], [19]. These approaches assumes a source distribution to be sparse, thus indirectly estimating both number and locations of the sources in simulations [18]–[20] and in real experiments [21], [22]. As a result, it replaces integer optimization with a sparsity-constrained, non-integer estimation of source parameters.

One limitation of this approach is the discretization of the PDE, which restricts the source locations to mesh elements and increases the number of unknown parameters to estimate. This over-parameterization negatively affects algorithm performance, particularly in the early stages with highly sparse source signals and limited measurements. Furthermore, the source localization accuracy is limited by the size of the mesh elements. In this work we propose a solution for this problem tailored to network of agents.

Our key contribution has two main aspects. First, we introduce a method that allows for beyond-the-grid, superresolution source localization. We model the source terms in a Poisson equation as a linear combination of Dirac measures with unknown support and weights. By applying a Bayesian framework and utilizing SBL, we enforce sparsity constraints on the source weights, thus estimating the number of the sources. Second, we propose a distributed algorithm that alternates between estimating source locations using gradient-based diffusion strategy over network [23], and estimating source support for fixed source locations. These steps only

require sharing estimates of source locations within the network and eliminate the need for a fusion center. We employ the adjoint state method [1], [24] for gradient computation, which is commonly used in inverse problems involving PDE constraints. This approach can be extended to other types of PDEs, accounting for factors such as advection or time-dependency in the process.

II. SIGNAL MODEL

Consider GSL over some d -dimensional exploration area Ω . We assume that the spatial gas concentration over Ω can be described by a time-invariant linear diffusion PDE (also known as Poisson equation) in the following form:

$$-\kappa\Delta f(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{l=1}^L w_l \delta_{\theta_l}(\Omega), \quad \mathbf{x} \in \Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^d \quad (1)$$

$$\text{s.t. } f(\mathbf{x}) = 0, \quad \mathbf{x} \in \partial\Omega, \quad (2)$$

where κ is a diffusion coefficient, $f(\mathbf{x})$ is a spatial gas concentration intensity, and Δ is a Laplace operator. The right-hand side (RHS) of (1) is a superposition of L gas sources – Dirac measures over Ω with a support $\theta_l \in \Omega$, and having release rates w_l , $l \in \mathcal{L} \triangleq \{1, \dots, L\}$. Equation (1) is augmented with a Dirichlet boundary condition (2) at the boundary $\partial\Omega$. We assume only a few gas source present, such that w_l , $l \in \mathcal{L}$ are sparse; i.e., not all possible gas sources are active. Furthermore, we will select L to exceed the true number of sources, which is sometimes referred to as *max-search* approach [25]. The model (1) and (2) thus represents a spatial distributions of the gas released from several (constant) sources in the absence of wind.

Assume for a moment that both w_l and θ_l , $l \in \mathcal{L}$ are known. $f(\mathbf{x})$ can then be obtained by solving (1) subject to (2) [26]. We use here a method of Green’s functions [27], which determines $f(\mathbf{x})$ as

$$f(\mathbf{x}) = \int_{\Omega} G(\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\theta}) \sum_{l=1}^L w_l \delta_{\theta_l}(\Omega) d\boldsymbol{\theta} = \sum_{l=1}^L w_l G(\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\theta}_l) \quad (3)$$

where $G(\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\theta})$ is a Green’s function defined as a solution to

$$-\kappa\Delta G(\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\theta}) = \delta_{\boldsymbol{\theta}}(\Omega), \quad \mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\theta} \in \Omega, \quad (4)$$

subject to the constraint $G(\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\theta}) = 0$, $\mathbf{x} \in \partial\Omega$; i.e., $G(\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\theta})$ is a ‘response’ of the PDE to a single source at the location $\boldsymbol{\theta}$.

Remark 1: We will assume that the solution to (4) exists and can be determined (see e.g., [27, Chap. 15.6-9]). In general, the Green’s functions, as required for our purposes, can be approximated, e.g., with a neural network [28]. We therefore leave the estimation of Green’s functions outside the scope of this work.

Now, consider a discretization of (1) where Ω is partitioned into N not necessarily regular grid cells. For each cell with center coordinates \mathbf{x}_i , $i \in \mathcal{N} \triangleq \{1, \dots, N\}$, we then assume a constant concentration value $f(\mathbf{x}_i) = \text{const}$. The corresponding concentrations are then aggregated into a vector \mathbf{f} with i th

element given by $[\mathbf{f}]_i = f(\mathbf{x}_i)$. Similarly, we define an $N \times L$ matrix $\mathbf{G}(\boldsymbol{\Theta})$ with i, j element $[\mathbf{G}(\boldsymbol{\Theta})]_{i,j} = G(\mathbf{x}_i, \boldsymbol{\theta}_j)$, $i \in \mathcal{N}$, $j \in \mathcal{L}$, where $\boldsymbol{\Theta} \triangleq [\boldsymbol{\theta}_1, \dots, \boldsymbol{\theta}_L]$. This allows us to rewrite (3) in a matrix-vector form as

$$\mathbf{f} = \mathbf{G}(\boldsymbol{\Theta})\mathbf{w} \quad (5)$$

with $\mathbf{w} \triangleq [w_1, \dots, w_L]^T$. Let us point out that while we discretized Ω , the location of the sources in the model (5) are not restricted to this grid and can take arbitrary values.

Consider now a network of K robotic agents. We will model the network with a strongly connected, weighted graph [23]. Assume now that each agent collects M_k , $k \in \mathcal{K} \triangleq \{1, \dots, K\}$, noisy samples of the concentration $f(\mathbf{x})$ at locations $\mathbf{x}_{m,k}$, $m = 1, \dots, M_k$. Furthermore, w.l.o.g. we assume that $N \gg M_k$ and that $\mathbf{x}_{m,k}$, $\forall m, k$, are a subset of discretization cells¹. The measurements of the agent k are collected in a vector $\mathbf{z}_k \in \mathbb{R}_k^{M_k}$ such that

$$\mathbf{z}_k = \boldsymbol{\Phi}_k \mathbf{f} + \boldsymbol{\xi}_k, \quad k \in \mathcal{K} \quad (6)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\Phi}_k \in \mathbb{R}^{M_k \times N}$ is a 0-1 selection matrix that indicates measured elements of \mathbf{f} . The perturbation $\boldsymbol{\xi}_k$ is assumed to be homoscedastic zero-mean Gaussian with precision matrix $\lambda_{\xi} \mathbf{I}$ for $\lambda_{\xi} > 0$.

Our goal now is to use $\mathbf{z} \triangleq [\mathbf{z}_1, \dots, \mathbf{z}_K]^T$ to cooperatively estimate a sparse vector \mathbf{w} , locations $\boldsymbol{\Theta}$, and recover \mathbf{f} from (5). To this end we pursue a Bayesian approach towards parameters estimation as detailed in the following.

A. Bayesian formulation of the inference model

Consider the following posterior probability density function (pdf) of the variables of interest:

$$p(\mathbf{f}, \mathbf{w}, \boldsymbol{\Theta} | \mathbf{z}) \propto p(\mathbf{z} | \mathbf{f}) p(\mathbf{f} | \mathbf{w}, \boldsymbol{\Theta}) p(\mathbf{w}) p(\boldsymbol{\Theta}), \quad (7)$$

where source locations $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ and their rates \mathbf{w} are assumed to be independent.

Based on (6) we immediately see that $p(\mathbf{z} | \mathbf{f}) = \prod_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{z}_k | \boldsymbol{\Phi}_k \mathbf{f}, \lambda_{\xi}^{-1} \mathbf{I})$ is a Gaussian likelihood function. The pdf $p(\mathbf{f} | \mathbf{w}, \boldsymbol{\Theta})$ encodes the deterministic relationship between sources and concentration \mathbf{f} based on (5). It can be modeled with a Dirac distribution $p(\mathbf{f} | \mathbf{w}, \boldsymbol{\Theta}) = \delta_{\mathbf{G}(\boldsymbol{\Theta})\mathbf{w}}(\mathbb{R}^N)$ over N -dimensional space \mathbb{R}^N . Concerning the prior $p(\boldsymbol{\Theta})$ we will assume it to be uniform over Ω , i.e., $p(\boldsymbol{\Theta}) \propto \text{const}$. In case of $p(\mathbf{w})$ we instead employ a modeling approach used in SBL [16].

SBL assigns a prior over \mathbf{w} so that its posterior estimate is sparse. This is done through a hierarchical factorable prior $p(\mathbf{w} | \boldsymbol{\gamma}) p(\boldsymbol{\gamma}) = \prod_{l=1}^L p(w_l | \gamma_l) p(\gamma_l)$, where $p(w_l | \gamma_l) = \mathcal{N}(w_l | 0, \gamma_l)$, $l \in \mathcal{L}$ [16], [29], [30]. For each $l \in \mathcal{L}$ the hyperparameters $\gamma_l \geq 0$, also called sparsity parameter, regulates the ‘width’ of $p(w_l | \gamma_l)$; the product $p(w_l | \gamma_l) p(\gamma_l)$ defines a so-called Gaussian scale mixture [31]. Obviously, when an estimate of $\gamma_l \rightarrow 0$, the prior $p(w_l | \gamma_l)$ collapses to a Dirac measure at the origin, driving the posterior estimate of w_l

¹As discretization of Ω is arbitrary, we can always select it to include measurement locations

towards 0. Popular selections of the hyperpriors $p(\gamma_l)$, $l \in \mathcal{L}$, are inverse Gamma [16], [32], [33], non-informative, i.e., $p(\gamma_l) \propto \gamma_l^{-1}$, [16], [34], and uniform, i.e. $p(\gamma) \propto 1$ [35]–[37]. Inference methods using the latter are called evidence maximization procedures [16], [17], [38]. Their virtue compared to other methods relying on other hyperprior selections is twofold [31]: they typically demonstrate superior (or similar) performance and very efficient implementations exist that can be analyzed [35]–[37], [39]. Here we consider the third choice for $p(\gamma_l)$, $l = 1, \dots, L$, i.e., uniform prior.

Now, the resulting posterior pdf becomes

$$p(\mathbf{f}, \mathbf{w}, \gamma, \Theta | \mathbf{z}) \propto p(\mathbf{z} | \mathbf{f}) p(\mathbf{f} | \mathbf{w}, \Theta) p(\mathbf{w}, \gamma) p(\Theta). \quad (8)$$

In what follows we propose an distributed optimization algorithm to iteratively maximize (8).

III. DISTRIBUTED SUPERRESOLUTION GSL

We begin with the estimation of γ by treating Θ fixed at $\hat{\Theta}$ and marginalize (8) over \mathbf{f} , which leads to

$$p(\mathbf{w}, \gamma, \hat{\Theta} | \mathbf{z}) = \int p(\mathbf{f}, \mathbf{w}, \gamma, \hat{\Theta} | \mathbf{z}) d\mathbf{f} \propto p(\mathbf{z} | \mathbf{w}, \hat{\Theta}) p(\mathbf{w}, \gamma)$$

By fixing Θ , we essentially linearize the problem, so that the resulting posterior coincides with that used in a standard SBL [16]. As such, we can re-use existing algorithms to maximize it. Specifically, we will use a distributed implementation of Fast Marginal Likelihood Maximization (FMLM) for SBL proposed in [40] to maximize it. The key steps of [40] specialized to our case are as follows. We define

$$\bar{\Phi} \triangleq \lambda_\xi \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \Phi_k^T \Phi_k, \quad \bar{\mathbf{z}} \triangleq \lambda_\xi \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \Phi_k^T \mathbf{z}_k \quad (9)$$

$$\mathbf{D} \triangleq \mathbf{G}(\hat{\Theta})^T \bar{\Phi} \mathbf{G}(\hat{\Theta}), \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{d} \triangleq \mathbf{G}(\hat{\Theta})^T \bar{\mathbf{z}}. \quad (10)$$

The quantities $\bar{\Phi}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{z}}$ can be computed distributively using an averaged consensus algorithm [41]. Moreover, they do not depend on the parameters of interest, can be computed only once before the optimization. In fact, they essentially “encode” measurement locations and measured values of all agents computed cooperatively.

Now, following [40] we consider the factorization $p(\mathbf{w}, \gamma, \hat{\Theta} | \mathbf{z}) = p(\mathbf{w} | \gamma, \hat{\Theta}, \mathbf{z}) p(\gamma, \hat{\Theta} | \mathbf{z})$. Here, $p(\mathbf{w} | \hat{\gamma}, \hat{\Theta}, \mathbf{z}) \propto p(\mathbf{z} | \mathbf{w}, \hat{\Theta}) p(\mathbf{w} | \hat{\gamma})$ can be shown to be Gaussian [35]. For given $\hat{\gamma}$ and using (10) its covariance matrix and mean are

$$\hat{\Sigma}_w = \left(\mathbf{D} + \hat{\Gamma}^{-1} \right)^{-1} \quad \text{and} \quad \hat{\mathbf{w}} = \hat{\Sigma}_w \mathbf{d} \quad (11)$$

respectively, where $\hat{\Gamma} \triangleq \text{diag}(\hat{\gamma})$. The second factor $p(\gamma, \hat{\Theta} | \mathbf{z}) \propto p(\mathbf{z} | \gamma, \hat{\Theta})$ is a key to the support γ estimation.

Specifically, $\hat{\gamma}$ is found as a minimizer of

$$\begin{aligned} C(\gamma) &\triangleq -\log p(\mathbf{z} | \gamma, \hat{\Theta}) = -\log \int p(\mathbf{z} | \mathbf{w}, \hat{\Theta}) p(\mathbf{w} | \gamma) d\mathbf{w} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \log |\Sigma_\gamma(\hat{\Theta})| + \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{z}^T \Sigma_\gamma(\hat{\Theta})^{-1} \mathbf{z} \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where $\Sigma_\gamma(\hat{\Theta}) \triangleq \lambda_\xi^{-1} \mathbf{I} + \bar{\Phi} \mathbf{G}(\hat{\Theta}) \Gamma \mathbf{G}(\hat{\Theta})^T \bar{\Phi}^T$, $\bar{\Phi} \triangleq [\Phi_1^T, \dots, \Phi_K^T]$, and $\Gamma \triangleq \text{diag}(\gamma)$. In [40] $C(\gamma)$ is optimized

component-wise. It was shown (see also [37], [40]) that with respect to γ_l its minimum is achieved at

$$\hat{\gamma}_l = \begin{cases} \frac{q_l^2 - s_l}{s_l^2}, & \text{if } q_l^2 > s_l, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

where parameters s_l and q_l are computed as

$$s_l = \frac{\gamma_l^{-1} S_l}{\gamma_l^{-1} - S_l}, \quad q_l = \frac{\gamma_l^{-1} Q_l}{\gamma_l^{-1} - S_l}, \quad (14)$$

with $S_l = [\mathbf{D} - \mathbf{D} \Sigma_w \mathbf{D}]_{ll}$ and $Q_l = [\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{D} \Sigma_w \mathbf{d}]_l$ defined using (10). The algorithms then evaluates (13) for all L components, essentially reducing $C(\gamma)$ in a coordinate-wise descent manner. Note that given (9) and estimates $\hat{\Theta}$ these steps do not require cooperation. Moreover, it can be shown [42] that such optimization of (12) is equivalent to a coordinate-wise minimization of a convex upper bound on $\mathcal{C}(\gamma)$, which ensures convergence to the minimizer.

Now let us turn our attention to location parameters Θ . Here we fix the support estimate $\hat{\gamma}$ and maximize the posterior $p(\mathbf{f}, \hat{\mathbf{w}}, \hat{\gamma}, \Theta | \mathbf{z})$ with respect to Θ . To this end we will use gradient-descent [43], which will also allow making use of diffusion strategies [23] to perform updates over a network. In the considered setting, the maximization of (8) is equivalent to the following optimization:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\Theta} \left\{ J(\Theta) \triangleq -\log p(\mathbf{z} | \mathbf{f}) = \frac{\lambda_\xi}{2} \|\mathbf{z} - \Phi \mathbf{f}\|^2 \right\} \quad (15) \\ \text{s.t. } g(\mathbf{f}, \Theta) \triangleq \mathbf{f} - \mathbf{G}(\Theta) \mathbf{w} = \mathbf{0} \end{aligned}$$

where both \mathbf{f} and \mathbf{w} are implicit functions of Θ . Consider now a single agent $k \in \mathcal{K}$ and its neighborhood $\mathcal{N}(k)$, which are agents directly connected to the agent k . We solve (15) using the combine-then-adapt (CTA) rule [23] by computing the following update at the iteration j :

$$\Psi_k = \sum_{l \in \mathcal{N}(k)} \alpha_{lk} \hat{\Theta}_l^{[j]}, \quad (\text{combination}) \quad (16)$$

$$\hat{\Theta}_k^{[j+1]} = \Psi_k - \mu \nabla_{\Theta} J(\Theta) |_{\Theta = \Psi_k} \quad (\text{adaptation}). \quad (17)$$

where α_{lk} , $k, l \in \mathcal{K}$, are graph edge weights, $\nabla_{\Theta} J(\Theta)$ is a gradient of (15) evaluated at Ψ_k and μ is an appropriately chosen step size. Note that we do not marginalize \mathbf{f} out, but use it to simplify the gradient computation with the adjoint state method (see e.g., [1], [24]) as follows. Let $\boldsymbol{\eta}$ be an adjoint variable defined as a solution to $\left(\frac{\partial g(\mathbf{f}, \Theta)}{\partial \mathbf{f}} \right)^T \boldsymbol{\eta} = - \left(\frac{\partial J(\Theta)}{\partial \mathbf{f}} \right)^T$. It is rather straightforward to show that

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\eta} &= -\lambda_\xi \bar{\Phi}^T (\Phi \mathbf{f} - \mathbf{z}) = (\bar{\mathbf{z}} - \bar{\Phi} \mathbf{f}) \quad (18) \\ &= \bar{\mathbf{z}} - \underbrace{\bar{\Phi} \mathbf{G}(\Theta) \left(\mathbf{G}(\Theta)^T \bar{\Phi} \mathbf{G}(\Theta) + \hat{\Gamma}^{-1} \right)^{-1} \mathbf{G}(\Theta)^T}_{\mathbf{f} = \mathbf{G}(\Theta) \mathbf{w}} \bar{\mathbf{z}}. \end{aligned}$$

Then, $\nabla_{\Theta} J(\Theta)$ can be evaluated as

$$\nabla_{\Theta} J(\mathbf{f}, \Theta) = \boldsymbol{\eta}^T \frac{\partial g(\mathbf{f}, \Theta)}{\partial \Theta} \quad (19)$$

where $\partial g(\mathbf{f}, \Theta)/\partial \Theta$ is a matrix with the l th column given by $\frac{\partial g(\mathbf{f}, \Theta)}{\partial \theta_l} = -\left[w_l \frac{\partial G(\mathbf{x}_0, \theta_l)}{\partial \theta_l}, \dots, w_l \frac{\partial G(\mathbf{x}_{N-1}, \theta_l)}{\partial \theta_l}\right]^\top$, $l \in \mathcal{L}$. Now, using (19), each agent can compute the CTA update (17), until some suitable convergence criterion is satisfied.

A. Algorithm implementation details

Let us now summarize the whole algorithm.

First, we initialize $\hat{\Theta}^{[0]}$ by suitably partition Ω into $\tilde{L} \geq N$ grid points θ_l , $l = 1, \dots, \tilde{L}$. Then, we compute $\bar{\Phi}$ and \bar{z} from (9) with averaged consensus and initialize support $\hat{\gamma}$ with the strategy proposed in [40]. Then, we can begin with update iterations, summarized in Algorithm 1 for an agent k .

Algorithm 1 Single iteration of the algorithm for agent k

- 1: **while** $\hat{\Theta}_k$ has not converged **do**
 - 2: $\Psi_k \leftarrow (16)$, $\eta \leftarrow (18)$, $\nabla_{\Theta} J(\Psi_k) \leftarrow (19)$
 - 3: Update $\hat{\Theta}_k^{[j+1]} \leftarrow (17)$
 - 4: **end while**
 - 5: $D, d \leftarrow (10)$
 - 6: **while** $\hat{\gamma}$ has not converged **do**
 - 7: **for** element l in $\hat{\gamma}$ **do**
 - 8: $s_l, q_l \leftarrow (14)$, $\hat{\gamma}_l \leftarrow (13)$
 - 9: **end for**
 - 10: Remove sources θ_l with $\hat{\gamma}_l = 0$, $\hat{\Sigma}_w, \hat{w} \leftarrow (11)$
 - 11: **end while**
-

Parameters Θ and γ are updated until parameter change is less than $< 1\%$. Algorithm 1 is repeated by each agent a fixed number of iterations, or until a suitable stopping criterion is met. The gradient update step μ is selected using Armijo rule [43], which can be performed locally by each agent.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

We now provide some simulation results to demonstrate the performance of the method. For simplicity, we will consider a Poisson equation in 1D, setting $\Omega = [0, 1]$ and $\kappa = 1$.

In this case the Green's function of the corresponding equation can be computed in closed form as $G(x, \theta) = x(1 - \theta)$ for $0 \leq x \leq \theta$ and $G(x, \theta) = -\theta(x - 1)$ for $\theta < x \leq 1$. We will generate 3 sources with rates set to 1 and locations selected as $\theta_1 = 0.2 + 0.05\epsilon_1$, and $\theta_i = \theta_{i-1} + 0.1 + 0.2a\epsilon_i$, $i = 2, 3$, where ϵ_i , $i = 1, \dots, 3$ are uniformly and independently drawn from a unit interval. Such source generation ensures their separability. For the algorithm we set $N = 100$ and equally split measurements between $K = 6$ agents. The used connectivity graph is a geometric graph with 50% connectivity; the weights α_{kl} , $k, l \in \mathcal{K}$, are selected according to the Laplacian rule [23].

We will compare the proposed distributed superresolution GSL (DSR-GSL) with two benchmarks strategies: its centralized version (C-GSL), and a centralized re-weighted LASSO (rLASSO) [35], [44]. For rLASSO we linearize the model by discretizing Ω into $5N$ points; as estimated sources we keep only the estimated weights with magnitudes $> 10^{-5}$, which should compensate for numerics of the solver. As metrics we use the estimated number of components \tilde{L} , the MSE

Fig. 1: Top: Estimated \tilde{L} ; Middle: Concentration MSE; Bottom: true positive rate (TPR) false positive rate (FPR).

between the estimated and true concentration \mathbf{f} , and true and false positive rates of source detections. As a detection we consider a source within $\pm \frac{1}{2N}$ of a true location. The results, averaged over 400 random runs, are shown in Fig. 1 for SNR=5dB (low) and SNR=30dB (high) regimes as functions of M . As we see in Fig. 1, all algorithms seem to introduce “artifacts” – small in amplitude (as seen from MSE plots), yet detected false sources. This is more pronounced for rLASSO, which seems to overfit the data as confirmed by the MSE and higher FPR. DSR-GSL and C-GSL remain more conservative in this respect, with DSR-GSL producing fewer artifacts, loosing a bit in MSE, but achieving similar TPR to the other methods, especially in high SNR regime. The discrepancy in MSE between DSR-GSL and C-GSL in high SNR regime is likely attributed to slight variations in location estimates between agents due to CTA rule. Nonetheless, DSR-GSL remains competitive with C-GSL: both bring reduction in complexity as compared to the $5N$ -dimensional rLASSO optimization, and generate fewer artifacts.

V. CONCLUSION

The results demonstrate the potential of the SBL method to localize sources beyond the grid resolution of the discretized PDE. Despite its nonlinear nature, the optimization algorithms rely only on network consensus for sparse location estimates. The methods, however, does require prior knowledge of the Green's function and its derivative, which in general is not always available. A possible extension of the method could thus make use of e.g., physics-informed neural networks, to approximate Green's function for GSL with general convection-diffusion models.

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